

Towards Automatic Segmentation: Preprocessing Histological Images with Filters and Contrast Enhancement

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Abstract— Chagas disease and toxoplasmosis are highly relevant to public health concerns. To investigate parasitic load and treatment efficacy, several studies have been conducted, with the quantification of intracellular parasites being a crucial step. Currently, this process is performed manually through microscopic observation, which limits the efficiency and standardization of the results. This work proposes the use of digital image processing techniques by applying filtering, contrast enhancement, and detection algorithms to improve the analysis of these images. In this study, 22 images were evaluated and processed using Python, applying Gaussian, Mean, and Bilateral filters, along with contrast enhancement techniques such as CLAHE and Unsharp Mask. The best combinations of filters and parameters were assessed using the Carneiro Contrast Index (CCI) and Neighborhood Valley Emphasis (NVE) metrics. The results indicated that CLAHE was more effective at enhancing contrast, while Unsharp Mask achieved better segmentability scores. It was concluded that a balance between CCI and NVE provides the most suitable approach to optimize image quality for subsequent segmentation.

Keywords— CLAHE, Contrast Enhancement, Digital Image Processing, Histological Images, Unsharp Mask.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chagas disease, caused by the protozoan *Trypanosoma cruzi*, and toxoplasmosis, caused by *Toxoplasma gondii*, are parasitic infections that are relevant in the context of congenital diseases. In Brazil, it is estimated that around 1.2 million people are infected with *T. cruzi*, while toxoplasmosis also represents a considerable risk due to its vertical transmission - from mother to fetus. [1-2]

With advances in biotechnology and public health research, *in vitro* cell models have been widely used to investigate infection mechanisms and the efficacy of therapeutic compounds. The quantification of intracellular parasites - such as *T. cruzi* amastigotes or similar structures in *T. gondii* - is a fundamental step in these studies, making it possible to assess the parasite load and the effect of the treatments tested [3].

However, this procedure is still carried out manually through microscopic observation, which is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and subject to inter-observer variability, compromising the standardization of results [4]. In this sense, the use of digital image processing techniques represents a promising alternative for automating the counting of cells or

parasites. By applying filters, contrast enhancement and detection algorithms, it is possible to develop computational tools capable of identifying and quantifying parasites in microscopic images with greater precision and reproducibility. Automating this process contributes not only to accelerating the analysis [5-6-7], but also to the reliability of the data obtained in laboratory studies.

Therefore, this study aims to develop an automated method for quantifying intracellular parasites in optical microscopy images, focusing on in vitro infection models of *T. cruzi* and *T. gondii*. The proposal seeks to digitize the parasite analysis process, enhancing the reproducibility, precision, and reliability of experimental studies.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this article, the image database used was provided by the Laboratório de Imunofisiologia da Reprodução (LABIFIR - Laboratory of Reproductive Immunophysiology) at the Federal University of Uberlândia. From the data, 22 images were selected for use in this analysis.

All 22 images were processed in each of the three groups, as described below:

- Group 1 (G1): corresponds to the control group, formed by the original images without any additional processing.
- Group 2 (G2): composed of images in RGB format;
- Group 3 (G3): composed of the original images converted to grayscale;

Therefore, the code for the filter application and contrast enhancement techniques was developed in the Python programming language using Visual Studio Code (VS Code) as the digital environment. Image processing was performed on a computer equipped with an Intel Core i5-13450HX processor and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 graphics card.

Initially, several filters were applied prior to the execution of contrast enhancement techniques was executed, since the goal was to avoid enhancing noise. The filters used were Gaussian, Bilateral, and Mean, with large ranges of their parameters, e.g., kernel sizes 3, 5, and 7. After completing this procedure, contrast enhancement methods were

presented using CLAHE with variation of parameters for Clip Limit and Tile Grid.

Additionally, the calibration of the unsharp mask is provided for the amount, radius, and threshold as well. In order to perform a metric analysis, the Carneiro Contrast Index (CCI) was used for contrast analysis and neighborhood valley emphasis (NVE) to study how segmentable the image was, which would provide better visual results.

A. Gaussian Filter

A Gaussian function describes a low-pass filter, as the major effect it permits low frequencies to pass through. Since noise is generally associated with high-frequency components, it returns an image with blurred edges, where the fine details may not be preserved. [8].

B. Mean Filter

The mean filter is a low-pass spatial filter that defines the mean of the pixel values in a specified kernel and replaces the center element of the neighborhood with this mean value. Thus, it further homogenizes the image by removing the local pixel value variations. [8].

C. Bilateral Filter

Finally, the tested filters also comprised the Bilateral filter, which consists of the weighted average of the pixels, also defined by the user, inside a local neighborhood, where the weights are dependent on both spatial distance and intensity difference. Thus, the noise is smoothed while the edges are retained. [9]

D. CLAHE

The CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) method is a contrast technique that, when applied, acts by dividing regions (TileGrid) in an image, whose size can be adjusted, performing a contrast enhancement function on each of them independently, based on a predefined clipping limit (Clip Limit). Thus, the difference in the magnitude of the pixels increases, consequently increasing the intensity difference in that region. [9]

E. Unsharp Mask

Unsharp Mask, which is another method of enhancing contrast. This involves subtracting a blurred version from the original image so that fine details are enhanced. In this method, it is usual to use either linear or nonlinear filters for high-frequency emphasis since high-frequency components carry information about the edges and fine details of an image. [10]

F. *Índice Carneiro de Contraste (ICC)*

The ICC is calculated as the standard deviation within 3×3 regions (kernels) over all pixels of the image, which generates a MAP by calculating, for each position, the standard deviation between the central pixel and its eight neighboring pixels. Each CCI output value reflects the local contrast within a specific kernel location. Output values will naturally fall into a new matrix identical in size to that of the input image, minus one pixel all around, due to zero-padding constraints normally imposed on most systems. [10]

G. *Neighborhood Valley Emphasis*

The NVE is a segmentation method, though since it comes by way of defining a valley point in an image and analyzing that particular point together with its neighboring pixels, it is important to emphasize that the neighborhood has an odd size so that the centering of the valley point can be maintained.

However, NVE may also be used as an index by interpreting its actual value as an indication of how well the image is segmentable and giving better visual images, i.e., a metric of separability based on the depths and contexts of the histogram valleys. [11]

III. RESULTS

The methodology, as described, resulted in 176 combinations between filters and contrast enhancement techniques by varying the parameters of both. It should also be observed that this process generated a total of 7,744 images.

Subsequently, the data were analyzed to determine the most effective contrast enhancement methods and their corresponding filtering combinations. Thus, a table is shared with three main numbers for CLAHE: one that matches the top ICC found, another that shows the average value, and the last one that matches the lowest value seen. The same spread was used for checking the Unsharp Mask. The parameter

combinations applied in this study are hereafter referred to as Config (1–6), as specified in table 1 legend.

Table 1: Mean ICC and NVE values for grayscale and RGB images, considering different enhancement configs.

	Grayscale		RGB	
	ICC	NVE	ICC	NVE
Original	2.8 ± 0.7	0.655 ± 0.158	2.8 ± 0.7	0.659 ± 0.093
Config 1	4.8 ± 0.9	0.424 ± 0.304	1.9 ± 0.4	0.472 ± 0.016
Config 2	3.5 ± 0.7	0.532 ± 0.359	1.4 ± 0.3	0.464 ± 0.022
Config 3	2.6 ± 0.5	0.627 ± 0.225	0.9 ± 0.2	0.472 ± 0.033
Config 4	2.9 ± 0.8	0.651 ± 0.158	1.6 ± 0.5	0.483 ± 0.042
Config 5	2.4 ± 0.6	0.654 ± 0.164	1.3 ± 0.3	0.479 ± 0.039
Config 6	2.1 ± 0.4	0.680 ± 0.167	0.9 ± 0.3	0.486 ± 0.040

Config 1: CLAHE (ClipLimit = 4.0, Tile 16x16) + Gaussian (kernel=5x5, $\sigma=1$)
Config 2: CLAHE (ClipLimit = 2.0, Tile 4x4) + Mean (3x3)
Config 3: CLAHE (ClipLimit = 1.0, Tile 16x16) + Mean (7x7)
Config 4: Unsharp (Amount = 1.0, Radius = 3, Threshold = 0) + Gaussian (kernel=3x3, $\sigma=0.5$)
Config 5: Unsharp (Amount = 1.0, Radius = 3, Threshold = 0) + Gaussian (kernel=7x7, $\sigma=2$)
Config 6: Unsharp (Amount = 1.5, Radius = 2, Threshold = 5) + Bilateral (d=9, $\sigma_color=25$, $\sigma_space=75$)

Moreover, these are the respective visual results for the parameter values, filters, and techniques previously applied.

Figure 1: (a): Original image without processing; (b) - G2 image processed with config 1 - G1 image processed with config 2; (d) - G2 image processed with config 3; (e) - G1 image processed with config 5; (f) - G2 image processed with config 6.

Figure 2 - ICC map after processing: (a) - Config 1; (b) - Config 4; (c) - Config 3; (d) - Config 6.

In the quantitative analysis of experimental group G3, the ICC revealed that the combination of CLAHE (ClipLimit=4.0, TileGridSize=16×16) and Bilateral Filter (d=5, $\sigma_{\text{color}}=25$, $\sigma_{\text{space}}=75$) achieved the highest mean of 4.87. This surpassed combinations with Mean Filter (3×3) and Gaussian Filter (kernel=5×5, $\sigma=1$), which yielded means of 4.81 and 4.79, respectively. Similarly, within its group, the Unsharp Mask technique (Amount=1.0, Radius=3, Threshold=0) combined with Gaussian Filter (kernel=3×3, $\sigma=0.5$) showed the highest mean of 2.93, outperforming combinations with Mean Filter (2.79) and Bilateral Filter

(2.72). These findings suggest that CLAHE was the most effective technique for enhancing overall image contrast.

Conversely, the NVE analysis for group G3 indicated that the Unsharp Mask technique produced the highest values. Specifically, the combination of Unsharp (Amount=1.5, Radius=2, Threshold=5) and Bilateral Filter (d=9, $\sigma_{\text{color}}=25$, $\sigma_{\text{space}}=75$) achieved a mean of 0.680 (Figure 1f). Notably, the same combination in group G2 resulted in a considerably lower mean of 0.486.

II. DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 1b, the CLAHE technique presented the most consistent quantitative results according to the calculated metrics, confirming its effectiveness in enhancing image contrast compared to the other evaluated methods [12]. The literature already indicates CLAHE as a powerful tool for local enhancement, minimizing noise and preserving details, which aligns with our findings. Visually, however, variations in the ClipLimit parameter of CLAHE directly affect image granularity and noise amplification [12]. This improvement in contrast, as well as the consequent increase in granularity, can be visually observed in the ICC map, Figures 2a and 2b.

In the context of contrast enhancement techniques, the literature generally addresses the methods separately. However, when testing different filters within the same dataset for CLAHE and Unsharp Mask, it was found that the application of different filters produces equivalent quantitative results, provided that the initial parameter for each technique is maintained. The lack of an in-depth discussion of this interaction in literature represents a gap that this study seeks to address. The observation that changing the filter alone is not sufficient for contrast enhancement corroborates the complementary nature of enhancement and filtering operations, as already expected and demonstrated in studies on video processing [13].

The superior performance of the Bilateral Filter in conjunction with enhancement techniques is already highlighted in the literature for its ability to preserve edges while smoothing noise [10], which justifies its performance. The inconsistency observed in the NVE, where the Unsharp Mask technique obtained the best results while CLAHE performed better in the ICC, suggests that these metrics are not directly proportional, indicating the need for joint

analysis for a comprehensive evaluation of the techniques' performance, thus requiring a visual analysis of the results [14]. Based on this qualitative analysis, it was observed that CLAHE had the worst results, with blurred and grainy images when compared to Unsharp Mask.

It can also be observed that group G2 did not achieve good results, indicating that the use of grayscale images is more appropriate for analysis and future segmentation. Finally, the best possible scenario is the balance between ICC and NVE. It should also be emphasized that a larger number of images is required for greater generalization of the study.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Although this study focused specifically on the preprocessing stage, the improvements observed in contrast and segmentability—measured by ICC and NVE—can have a direct impact on later steps, such as automatic segmentation based on thresholding or deep learning. By exploring different combinations of filters and contrast enhancement techniques, this work aimed to identify configurations that improve image quality in a way that supports more accurate and reliable analysis in future segmentation tasks.

Based on the analysis of the evaluated parameters, it is concluded that the balance between ICC and NVE provides the best visual results, proving to be more effective for future segmentation. Unsharp (Amount = 1.0, Radius = 3, Threshold = 0) + Gaussian (kernel=3×3, $\sigma=0.5$), as it presented the best mean values compared to the original image, also maintained the balance between ICC and NVE. For future work, it is recommended to balance these metrics in order to optimize object segmentation.

These results are based on a specific set of images from in vitro cultures containing intracellular parasites. Although the trends observed in the ICC and NVE metrics help to understand how different filtering and enhancement techniques behave, it's important to recognize that these findings may not apply universally. Further studies are needed to verify whether similar patterns hold across other staining methods, tissue types, or image magnifications.

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